

**THE INFLUENCE OF MODERN METHODS OF PREPARATION ON
THE CONDITION OF DENTAL TISSUES IN ORTHOPEDIC
DENTISTRY**

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Introduction: In this article, we consider the problem of treatment of secondary dementia and its relevance to the physiological artificial type. Ability to support the tooth to maintain proven viability. Analysis of the material makes it possible to identify the main pathogenic factors of root preparations that affect the condition of the pulp. Comparative characteristics of lasers used to provide medical care to dentists are displayed. Ability to use them in dental operations with.

Keywords: anatomy, fashion, orthopedic dentistry, pulp condition, laser, adentia.

Annotation: In recent decades, modern applied dentistry has developed not only through the introduction of new methods of prevention, diagnosis and treatment of dental diseases, but also through the improvement of dental equipment, increasing demands on patients and gradual development of dentistry promotes the improvement of the quality of treatment. The development of technology requires the knowledge and manual work of specialists. New technologies in the hands of a dentist who does not know his or her expertise can harm the health of the patient [4]. Dental diseases, in which defects appear in the hard tissues of the teeth and gums, always stimulate the development of science and technology. According to the World Health Organization, the percentage of some tooth defects is 75% of the population in different parts of the world. Tooth caries and high incidence of periodontal disease are the most important problems in dental medicine. To replace defects of teeth and dental hard tissues, non-removable artificial crowns and bridges

are used (according to the instructions), which support the periodontal masticatory pressure of the teeth. With this type of prosthesis, the masticatory effect can be restored to 100%, without affecting the taste, temperature, psychological and functional adaptation of the patient to fixed prostheses much faster than with removable prostheses. Dental preparation is an important stage of treatment with non-removable dentures, for which a large number of hard tissues supporting the teeth are removed, thereby damaging the hard tissues. teeth and dental pulp. High-quality preparation determines the service life of the continued restoration. Therefore, at this stage of treatment with artificial structures made of cast, combined and full ceramics, the dentist must adhere to five basic principles: 1. Make the dental tissue as hard as possible. and stability of the repair. 3. To achieve a high power restoration. 4. To achieve an optimal finish - suitable for restoration. 5. Maintain the health of the periodontal tissues. Sometimes it is necessary to abandon one theory in favor of another. In some cases, dental hard tissue is highly harvested to generate a volume sufficient to achieve esthetic requirements, high strength, and close fit of indirect restorative structures [2.5]. By analyzing the material, it becomes possible to study the main damage factors and pulpal reaction in response to pulp preparation using various conventional tooth abrasives (using rotary tooth abrasives) and alternative methods (different types of lasers). Long-term results of crown preparations showed high levels of pulp necrosis found in post-veneered preparations (5.1%) and non-orthodontic patients (0.5%) after artificial crown preparation (13.3%) [8]. The reaction of the pulp in response to cavity and crown preparation depends on many factors. These include friction, crossing of tooth germ processes, vibration, drying of dentin, contact with the pulp, lubricating layer, thickening of the remaining dentin, and exposure to temperature due to acid treatment . The importance of using a water-air spray during the preparation of thermally damaged cavities is already well known. When dentin is treated with a rotating boron or abrasive head, a significant amount of frictional

heat is generated. If an increase in temperature occurs during prolonged treatment without a cooling cavity or a large number of hard dental tissues, the dental pulp can be severely damaged. Scientific studies have shown that heat exposure to the pulp during treatment is the greatest stress. In the absence of cooling, the pulp temperature can rise to a critical level - from ambient to 11.6. As a result, the hemodynamics of the vessels changes, with subsequent damage to peripheral cells with necrosis. [8] When using water cooling, the pulp reaction is negligible. Also, when prepared with a water-cooled high-speed tip, the temperature of the toothpaste decreases due to the low temperature of the cooling water at the time of spraying and its high heat capacity. Analyzing the results of the study, it was proposed to cool the tooth surface treated with a water-air spray from a high-speed tip for 5 seconds before the start of preparation. After the start of the preparation of dental hard tissues, it is recommended to prepare periodically (time 4 seconds), then stop for 1 second. At the same time, the degree of cooling intensity should be determined by the consumption of water at least 50 ml per minute [1, 8]. When preparing hard dental tissues using air cooling at the beginning of the process, the dental pulp is cooled. But in the future, the temperature rises sharply to a sharp temperature. It should also be noted that the increase in friction temperature with the preparation of solid dental tissue depends on the rotational speed of the working tool and its torque, the pressure on the treated surface, the cooling effect of the detergent, the abrasive material and the size of the tool. 2,3]. The intersection of the dental process and the consequence of removing the outer part of that dental process are frequent consequences of the preparation of cavities or crowns. Histological examination showed that partial cutting of this process does not lead to the death of dental platelets. According to the results of several cytological studies, including microsurgery, it is known that the restoration of the cell membrane occurs immediately after the cellular process has passed. However, the detachment of the tooth germ process close to the cell body can lead to irreversible damage and cell

death. Subsequently, a single eruption that has lost viability is separated and replaced by bone marrow cells. [7] The layers of predentin closely related to each other form a semi-permeable barrier that prevents the penetration of harmful substances from the dentin. Damage to the platelet brushing destroys this layer and increases its permeability, which can have a negative effect on the condition of the pulp [8]. The effect of vibrations occurring during the operation of high-speed chips on the pulp has been little studied. The total number of lesions is known to occur both in the pulp cavity of the tooth, in the projection of the contact point between the boron and the dentin, and in other places far from the prepared site. Strong finger pressure with the fingertips should be avoided, since the vibration waves become especially noticeable when the rotation speed of the boron decreases and the drying speed of the dentin decreases. When a new part of the dentin is dried by the gas flow, capillary forces are activated in the dentin channels, and the fluid in the channels moves rapidly outward. This can lead to a narrowing of the tooth in the lumen. Such displaced teeth quickly die, disappear and decay on their own. Typically, these cells are replaced and the production of replacement dentin begins in 1-3 months [8]. According to the hydrodynamic theory of pain, excessive drying of the dentin can cause tooth sensitivity after surgery, since irritation and irritation of the nerve endings occurs. The tooth cavity, which opens the opening of the important tooth cavity, is the result of the formation of an irregular shape and the formation of a tail cone, which allows the safety zone during preparation and the topographical features of the location of the tooth cavity to be ignored. This complication usually occurs when an isolated tooth is mistakenly standing on the dental arch. In this case, it is necessary to fully diagnose and analyze the clinical model in order to provide an appropriate approach to the preparation of a supported tooth for further orthopedic treatment. The lubricating layer is an amorphous layer of fine grains, formed by rolling or making with hand tools on the surface of the dentin and in the dentin canals, 1-2 mm thick. The layer of lubrication reduces the

permeability of the dentin by about 85% and controls the barrier. Firstly, a small number of microorganisms are present in the lubricating layer. The presence of microflows leads to a significant increase in the number of bacteria, the destruction of the edges and the integrity of the fixed material layer. Pathological microorganisms and their metabolic products through the dentin channels can cause infection and pulpitis. To maintain the barrier function and protect the pulp, it is recommended to remove the lubricating layer from the surface of the dentin and replace it with a hybrid layer. It is also necessary to produce an accurate indirect repair with a minimum thickness of fixing material that achieves durability, integrity and structural [6-8] stress. The residual thickness of the dentin is the diameter of the dentin channels, their number increases as they approach the pulp, i.e. the permeability of the dentin increases the depth of preparation. The permeability of the dentin is of fundamental importance when assessing the degree of damage to the pulp during the treatment process. According to Stanley, the thickness of the remaining dentin is 2 mm, and the pulp is preserved from most restorative work, following all precautions [7, 8]. In order to prevent damage to the dental pulp, it is recommended to keep the remaining thickness of the dentin at least 1 mm. To determine the maximum depth of preparation, it is necessary to use the protection zone according to Abolmasov and Clive. You can also use the device preparation meter (Hager verken). [2] To reduce the chances of various complications, alternative methods of preparation of hard tooth tissues are constantly being sought and implemented. Therefore, in modern dentistry, various types of lasers are used. The medium that produces the laser beam is the main indicator that determines the main effect of the laser. Clinical practice included carbon dioxide (CO₂), erbium (EB), neodymium (nd), argon and diode lasers. Other substances (yttrium, aluminum and garnet [YAG]) are also added to the composition of the active environment. Laser photons interact with human tissue in different ways (they can be reflected, transparent, diffused and absorbed) and can

be used for various processes. For example, when a laser beam is irradiated, all its energy passes through the tissue and does not cause any shock or damage. During scattering, the energy of the laser beam is distributed in the tissue volume, resulting in a low-intensity thermal effect. In the process of absorption, the energy of the laser beam is converted into thermal energy. The main requirement for alternative preparation methods is the preparation of the finished surface to ensure high-quality processing and fixed repair, preserving the viability of the pulp. For this reason, the possibility of using lasers in dentistry is being studied and research is being carried out [6]. Laser conductivity of dentin Due to the high penetration of laser light through dentin, its energy can be absorbed by the pulp. As a result, the temperature of the pulp can change, which can then lead to irreversible damage. This characteristic of laser radiation was investigated using a block of 1 mm thick dentin, an energy meter and various laser beams. 17% of the diode laser beam and 27% of the Nd:YAG laser beam were found to pass through a 1 mm layer of dentin. In experiments with erbium and carbon dioxide lasers, almost no light was transmitted (the beam was absorbed or reflected). Clinical data show that erbium and carbon dioxide lasers cause less damage to the pulp than neodymium and diode lasers. [7] Carbon dioxide laser Carbon dioxide lasers are widely used in surgery on soft tissues in the oral cavity. Its effect allows the separation of soft tissues with simultaneous coagulation of blood vessels. The carried out research made it possible to determine the effect of a low-energy laser (1 W) on a cat tooth with a residual dentin thickness of 2.6 mm. The intensity of blood flow to the pulp increased by 50% (measurements were made using laser Doppler measurements). This indicates that painful blood vessels dilate in response to temperature stimuli. With an average increase in energy (up to 5w), an irreversible decrease in nutrition occurred (evidence of pulp damage). Overheating is the biggest cause of a decrease in blood supply. Therefore, the safety of carbon dioxide laser systems for the treatment of pathologies of solid dental tissues is currently under review. Nd:YAG

laser pulses with a wavelength of 1064 μm are the most investigated laser systems used in dental medicine. The effect of neodymium lasers on dental pulp may vary depending on the residual thickness of dentin. The results of the study showed that when using a laser with an impact energy of 100 MJ and a frequency of 10 pulses for 10 seconds, the pulp blood flow did not change significantly when treated with intact enamel. Laser After treating shallow cavities (residual dentin thickness of 1 mm), the blood flow to the pulp increased moderately and the damage was irreversible at high energy levels. Indicators such as the number of pulses per second play an important role. Significant structural abnormalities were observed when the laser was exposed to a specific area for more than 10 seconds. If the exposure exceeds 15 seconds, a funnel is formed in the tooth tissue (it almost reached the pulp). Data from the results of the study show that the neodymium laser has a beneficial effect on the dentin, but not on the dental pulp. The effect on the pulp consists in nerve damage and bleeding, causing irreversible damage, the severity of which depends on the characteristics of the laser radiation used during preparation. An important step in the study of lasers is to determine the energy level for a certain dentin thickness. This allows to achieve the desired effect without damaging the pulp. Er:YAG laser The erbium laser tooth preparation mechanism is based on the high absorption of its light by the aqueous components of the dental hard tissue. This can lead to a sharp increase in the temperature of a small amount of tissue. Both enamel and dentin are removed partly by microbursts and partly by long-term evaporation . Studies using scanning electron microscopes have shown that dentin channels open after laser treatment. These anatomical and structural data indicate the possibility of rapid fluid movement in dentin channels during laser dissection, which leads to nerve stimulation according to hydrodynamic principles. High-speed tip and ground: By isolating the V-shaped and orbital spaces of the teeth of experimental animals (dogs), a comparative study of anatomy with a YAG laser was carried out. Participants of this laboratory experiment were produced at high

speed using a YAG laser (maximum speed 100-200 MJ, frequency 10 pulses / sec), saving water. After preparation, the cavities are closed with glass fiber cement. All specimens were divided into two groups according to the residual thickness of the dentin. Histopathological comparison after pulp preparation by various methods was carried out after 1, 2, 4, 7 and 28 days. After high-speed boron preparation, a smooth surface covered with a layer of oil is obtained. The surface prepared by the laser is granular and rough, the dentin tubules are open, and fragments of the crushed layer are present. One day after treatment, histopathological reactions of various severity were observed in all cavities, regardless of their depth and preparation method. Displacement and contraction of the tooth bladder, infiltration by inflammatory cells, bleeding under the preparation area were observed. These histopathological changes were more pronounced after dental treatment: I used laser. After 7 days, the pulp reaction was weaker in teeth with superficial cavities, unlike in teeth with deep cavities. With both treatments, histopathological changes are limited to the pulp area adjacent to the drug site. After 28 days, regeneration of the blastocyst layer was observed in teeth treated with boron and laser. In the group of teeth with superficial cavities (large residual dentin thickness), the pulp was almost normal without obvious histopathological changes, regardless of the preparation technique. In both groups, the pulp reaction was absent or insignificant, which indicates the possibility of complete recovery and protection of the globe. YAG laser treatment of the pulp [7].

Conclusion: To select a critical tooth as a support in the treatment of partial secondary dementia, several factors must be taken into account. Various preparation methods have their advantages and disadvantages, and the rules of their application must be strictly followed when preparing teeth. It is also necessary to take into account the properties of various restorative materials and their adhesion to the prepared surfaces of hard dental tissues. Modern dentistry allows you to perform high-quality interventions without the manifestation of various

complications, which ensures the durability and esthetics of structures, which are subsequently interconnected.

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